

Emerging Trends in EdTech

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ABSTRACT

Education is most important facet for development. Education, training, and research are an integral and integrated parts each other. All these are responsible and dedicated for the better and healthy knowledge cultivation. Educational Institutions are responsible for the dedication of knowledge activities such as collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination of knowledge and similar activities. India is a developing country and growing fast to reach a status of developed nation education is a vital source and facets. Development of a country as a whole many a ways depends on the subjects and fields having applied in nature. Information Technology and Computing related subjects are playing a great for the complete and modern development of society. Even education systems have changed with the integration and application of Information Technology. The growths of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) are rapid in recent past as far as India is concerned. The increasing number of institutions, universities, especially self-financed is eye-catching. There are many merits and demerits of such type of institutions. The present paper is a kind of review one but also deals with the basics of policies that may be applied in future. Paper is presented many knowledge aspects in terms of a basic overview of institutions, numbers, engineering sectors, computing fields etc. in a brief manner.

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Introduction

Education is the driving force for the development of every kind. India is witnessed of various types of educational institutions established by many emperors in middle age to British Age. The Ancient India also holds a significant profile of Nalanda University, Taxila University etc. The growth of education brings development and improved science and technological affairs. Indian subcontinent begins its development during the Indus Valley Civilization as far as science and technology is concerned. Science and technology developed rapidly after India's independence After Independence, Republic of India has been started many traditional and nontraditional programs and subjects such as automobile engineering, information technology, communication [1], [7],[10]. Even it has started few other subjects such as space, polar, and nuclear sciences. As far as Information Technology is concerned many subjects have developed during late of 1990's.

Information technology basically consisting of two major division i.e. IT services and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO). It has the immense contribution in Indian Economy from 1.2% GDP in 1998 to 7.5% in 2012. As far as NASSCOM is concerned the sector is growing with other allied services emerged recent past viz. SaaS, and aggregated revenue of US\$160 billion in 2017. Importantly export revenue there started at US\$99 billion whereas household revenue at US\$48 billion. Importantly it is growing by over 13%. It is worthy to note that USA is responsible for about 60 % of Indian IT exports. There are many subjects are available and running for the solid promotion of the Indian IT sector such as—

- *Computer Science.*
- *Computer Science and Engineering.*
- *Computer Applications.*
- *Information Technology.*

Information Technology is responsible for the massive employment generation in India as far as software development is concerned. Indian Information Technology industry is directly employing about 2.8 million people. Moreover, it is also responsible for and indirect employment of about 8.9 million [2], [9], [14]. It is worthy to note that India is facing challenges of globalization from some countries such as China and Philippines due to their significant efforts into IT sector [3], [6], [10].

Information Age is most important asset in the current scenario. It has enabled create a great relationship and deal with the United States and European Countries. The following are few IT hubs in India (please refer Table 1). Though, apart from these few other cities and zones are also become popular such as Noida, Gurgaon, Kolkata etc.

Educational development plays an important role in the development of Information Technology infrastructure in India. Universities, research centres, colleges, and higher educational institutions are responsible for creating a sustainable environment for knowledge [4], [5], [20].

Table: 1-Top IT Hubs in India

Rank	Popular Destination of IT Activities
	Bangalore
	Chennai
	Hyderabad
	Mumbai
	Pune

Objective and Agenda

The main aim and objective of this paper include gather basics of Education and Training in India. It is a basic and theoretical paper with few on policy affairs. Some of the core agenda of this paper includes (but not limited to)—

- To learn about Education Systems in India from past to modern age including types of educational institutes and their focus.

- To dig out the educational regulatory bodies governing in India in various fields including their place etc.
- To learn about the role of educational systems that leads Information Technology and Computing industry in India.
- To learn about the Information Technology and Computing fields in India compare to other parts of the globe.
- To learn about few good engineering institutes and universities in India based on NIRF Ranking released by the Government of India (MHRD).
- To dig out the current strength of technical, management education in India including available degrees in different perspectives.

Methodology

The present study is conceptual and interdisciplinary in nature. It deals with educational aspects and affairs to learn about the Education Systems in India, the current strength of technical, management education in India and also educational regulatory bodies governing in India in various fields including their place. Hence for doing the research work mixed mode of methodologies have been adopted. Review of literature plays a vital role to dig out questions that are proposed in this work. Moreover few other affairs such as web survey also been carried out in respective websites such as UGC, AITCE, PCI, BCI, MCI, DCI, ICMR etc. Moreover to find out and show few best universities in modern India, the NIRF ranking played a vital role.

India: An Overview

India is located in South Asia and it is the seventh largest country in terms of area as well as it holds the second most popular country tag with 1.2 billion people on its surface. A place to ancient Indus valley civilization, India is also a historic place where several empires ruled out. India is also well-known for many interesting and vast, huge cultural heritage for the religious purpose as well [5], [11], [15].

Here religion of Hinduism, Buddhism, Jainism and Sikhism etc stayed together. Location wise, India is bounded by the Indian Ocean on the South. On the South West the Arabian Sea is there. Whereas Bay of Bengal is located in the areas of South east. The boundaries of India are with China, Nepal, Bhutan in the portion of north east. Burma, as well as Bangladesh are located the east of the nation. In the West, Pakistan is located. Indian Ocean neighbors place is Srilanka and the Maldives [8], [12], [19].

India is the world tenth largest economy in terms of GDP and it is also third longest in purchasing power. During 1991 and onwards major activities were started and today it is one of the largest as well as the fastest increasing major economy in the world. However, it is important to note that there are many challenges major concern of Indian economy and among the few important are include—

- Poverty*
- Corruption and Dishonesty*
- Malnutrition and undernourishment*

- Inadequate public healthcare systems
- Environmental Issues
- Terrorism etc

It is a federal and a multi-ethnic nation and also governed by a parliamentary system having 29 states and 7 union territories. Its parliament has two house viz. upper house and lower house. Rajya Sabha is Upper house whereas and the Lower house is called Lok Sabha. Importantly it is a pluralistic, multilingual society. The brief note on India is illustrated in Table 2. **Table-2- Some basic information of India**

Object	Value/ Characteristics
<i>Capital of India</i>	New Delhi
<i>Largest City of India</i>	Mumbai
<i>Government Structure</i>	Federal / Constitutional Republic
<i>Legislature Systems</i>	Upper House and Lower House
<i>Area of India</i>	3,287,590 square K.M.
<i>Water share</i>	9.6 %
<i>Population in India</i>	1,210,193,444 in 2011
<i>GDP (about)</i>	5.425 Trillion dollar
<i>Currency in India</i>	Indian Rupee

Higher Educational Institutes in India

India, like population and area in terms of educational system also holds a rank in the world with over 750+ universities [10], [16], [17]. Table 3 is showing details on universities in this regard. Such universities have established in a different way like—

- Government Universities
 - State University (i.e. State Funded & Management Universities)
 - Central University (i.e. Central Government Funded & Management Universities)
- Self Financed Universities
 - Private Universities (Passed by the state legislative assembly)
- Deemed Universities
 - Deemed to be a University (mainly upgraded from a college of repute and excellence)

Importantly India has over 40000+ colleges in professional, general levels. Such colleges not only offer Bachelors Degree level education but also Masters Degree in many cases. Some of the colleges offered Ph.D. and Doctoral Programs as well.

90+ Institute of National Importance (INI) are another important features and milestone in Indian education systems. These are treated as super-specialty systems catering areas and subjects such as Engineering, Management, Basic & Applied Science, Architecture, Pharmaceutical Sciences, Medical Sciences etc. Please refer Table 4 for more about such institutions etc. These are established and funded by the Central Government but given higher priorities than central Universities. Many a time, these are treated as higher importance among the students and common people than that of centrally funded universities etc. Apart from these few institutions are also established and funded by Govt. of India and most of these are research centers such as Bose Institute, Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics etc. the number of institutes in this category is about 200+.

Table: 3- Showing Indian Universities at a glance

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Central Universities		Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities		Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities		Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities		Except some states and UT

Table: 4- Showing Indian Higher Educational Institutes at a glance [12]

INI/ Higher Educational Institutions	In Numbers	Location
Indian Institute of Technology [IITs]		Bhubaneswar, Chennai, Delhi, Gandhinagar, Guwahati, Hyderabad, Indore, Jodhpur, Kanpur, Kharagpur, Mandi, Mumbai, Patna, Ropar, Roorkee and Varanasi
Indian Institute of Information Technology [IITs]		Gwalior, Allahabad, Jabalpur, Kancheepuram, Sri City, Guwahati, Vadodara, Kota, Trichy, Una, Sonapat, Kalyani, Lucknow, Dharwad, Kurnool, Kottayam, Manipur, Nagpur, Pune, Ranchi, Surat, Bhopal, Bhagalpur

National Institute of Technology [NITs]		Agartala, Allahabad, Arunachal Pradesh, Bhopal, Calicut, Delhi, Durgapur, Goa, Puducherry, Hamirpur, Jaipur, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Jalandhar, Jamshedpur, Kurukshetra, Nagpur, Patna, Raipur, Rourkela, Sikkim, Silchar, Srinagar, Surat, Karnataka, Tiruchirappalli, Uttarakhand, Warangal
Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology [IESTs]	1 (4 are in process)	Shibpur (West Bengal)
Indian Institute of Management [IIMs]		Calcutta, Ahmedabad, Bangalore, Lucknow, Kozhikode, Indore, Shillong, Rohtak, Ranchi, Raipur, Tiruchirappalli, Udaipur, Kashipur
Indian Institute of Science Education and Research [IISERs]		Calcutta, Mohali, Thiruvanthapuram, Pune, Bhopal
Other Central Funded Higher Educational Cum Research Institutes	Approximately 150+	Pan India with 28 States and UT

Higher Educational Institutes in India: Some Regularity Bodies

The higher education system in India is basically governed by the concerned Ministries. Centrally these are managed and regulated under MHRD i.e. Ministry of Human Resource Development. Though it is established and closely working with other institutions and organizations. State Higher Education Department of each state is a caretaker of the State Education affairs with close direction and relationship of MHRD and respective council. MHRD constitute many regulatory and administrative bodies throughout different sectors [11], [18], [23]. Among such UGC or University Grants Commission is playing a good role. Such institutions and bodies have been listed as follows—

MHRD—

The Ministry of Education, Government of India was the previous body and nomenclature until 25 September 1985 before renaming as Ministry of Human Resource Development. The main and core objectives of the Ministry are included but not limited to the following—

- Designing, formulation, and implementation of the National Policy related to the Education. It has also responsible for the policies and planned undertaken must be implemented with spirit.
- Among other roles of MHRD, another important is improving quality of the educational institutions and universities throughout the country. The ministry is working hard for the implementation and delivery of education in all the areas of nation including in regions where easy access to education is quite difficult.

- The MHRD through its scholarship etc. is always offering financial support to the disadvantaged groups (viz. poor, females and the minorities etc.)
- Offering loan subsidy, etc. for the deserving students from the different sections of the society is another motto of MHRD.
- MHRD is also responsible and dedicated with better cooperation in the field of education of international bodies, corporation including UNESCO etc. The ministry also responsible and able in better relationship with foreign governments for collaboration of the Universities etc. for offering enhanced education systems in the country.

The MHRD is responsible and also dedicated to the human resources in India. MHRD basically constitute with two departments—

1. The Department of School Education and Literacy (it is basically responsible for the primary, secondary and higher secondary education affairs initially and later on it has added adult education and literacy into its agenda).
2. Department of Higher Education (it mainly deals with higher education, research systems under universities and similar institutions. The core roles of this unit include university education, technical education, scholarship, and so on).

Among the core and allied activities of MHRD one of the important is offering and modernizing Languages education in the country specially Indian Languages etc. Hence to perform this role it is governed few Deemed Universities in the areas of Sanskrit, viz. Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan (RSKS) located in New Delhi, Shri Lal Bahadur Shastri Rashtriya Sanskrit Vidyapeeth (SLBSRSV) located in New Delhi, Rashtriya Sanskrit Vidyapeeth (RSV) situated in the city of Tirupati. However important to note that apart from these few other organizations and bodies also governed by the MHRD such as—

1. Kendriya Hindi Sansthan (KHS) which is located at Agra
2. English and Foreign Language University (EFLU) which is located at Hyderabad
3. National Council for Promotion of Urdu Language (NCPUL) which is located at New Delhi
4. National Council for Promotion of Sindhi Language (NCPSL) which is located at Vadodara

However, apart from these few other organizations that take care by the MHRD are include Commission for Scientific & Technological Terminology which is located at New Delhi; and another major name in the areas is Central Institute of Indian Languages (CIIL), Mysore, Karnataka, India [11], [21], [24].

UGC—

The University Grants Commission (UGC) established by the Government of India and it is a statutory body under UGC Act 1956. UGC is established and worked under Ministry of Human Resource Development. It is also charged for the deliberation and maintenance of standards of

higher education as far as University systems are concerned. Among the core role of the UGC few important are include—

- Providing recognition to universities in India including offshore campus of Indian Universities.
- Disburses funds to the recognized universities as well as colleges for the advancement of education, research and training.

UGC has its headquarters at New Delhi. However for its better and smooth operation it has established and six regional centres located in Pune, Bhopal, Kolkata, Hyderabad, Guwahati, and Bangalore.

AICTE—

All India Council for Technical Education is abbreviated as AICTE located at New Delhi. It is the statutory body responsible for the promotion of the technical education of the nation. It is under Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India. It has in 1987 as statutory body by an Act of Parliament. Among the core jobs of the university few important and valuable are—

- Proper planning as well as coordination in development of the technical education including (Pharmaceutical Education, Architecture, Hotel Management and Catering Technology, Computer Applications, Town and Country Planning) and management education system in India.
- The AICTE basically accredits postgraduate as well as graduate programs in technical subjects under specific categories at Indian institutions as per its charter/norms.

Like University Grants Commission (UGC) The AICTE also has various regional offices at different parts of the country for better functioning Kanpur, Chandigarh, Gurgaon, Guwahati, Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai, Mumbai, Bhopal, Baroda, Kolkata and Thiruvananthapuram. The AICTE basically functioned for the following bodies and Bureau—

- ✓ Planning and Co-ordination Bureau and Academic Bureau
- ✓ University Bureau
- ✓ Administration Bureau
- ✓ e-Governance Bureau
- ✓ Approval Bureau
- ✓ Finance Bureau
- ✓ Research, Institutional and Faculty Development Bureau

Normally Board of Studies are responsible for the dealing of educational affairs in the areas of undergraduate engineering, postgraduate engineering, architecture. Apart from these areas such as town and country planning, pharmacy, management, applied arts and crafts, hotel management and catering technology (HMCT) education are also governed and managed by the BoS of All India Council for Technical Education. It is important to note that as per order of Supreme Court of the country Engineering Degrees, Computer Applications Degrees, Management Degrees

offered under University (not in a affiliating colleges) does not required any kind of Approval of the AICTE. However, such Universities have to maintain their quality and standards, norms as laid down by the AICTE. After this notification a large number of Deemed Universities, Private Universities, and even Government Universities are also offering such degrees under their own capacity and statute [20], [22], [24]. Many universities have started a different kind of M.Tech program which is also not under the preview of AICTE called *M.Tech (By Research)* as a research based program or Technological Research program with capacity of internal or external research. As a whole AICTE granted about 10,000 institutions (Detail of Data as on 2015-16 depicted in Table 5).

Table: 5 - Approved Institutions with Intake for 2015-16 (Source AICTE Handbook)

Region	State	Approved Programmes			Approved Intake			Total	Total
		Diploma	PG	UG	Diploma	PG	UG	Approved Institutions	Approved Intake
Central	Chhattisgarh				11502		23706		39984
	Gujarat				72670	32745	76704		182119
	Madhya Pradesh				36676	47465	110446		194587
Central Total					120848	84986	210856		416690
Eastern	Andaman and Nicobar Islands								
	Arunachal Pradesh								
	Assam								
	Jharkhand								19794
	Manipur								
	Meghalaya								
	Mizoram								
	Nagaland								
	Odisha				47015	17011	48959		112985
	Sikkim								
	Tripura								
West Bengal				34962	13422	41038		89422	
Eastern Total					96097	36255	105508		237860
North-West	Chandigarh								
	Delhi					13403	10080		29348

	Haryana				72488	30196	70394		173078
	Himachal Pradesh				10858		10660		24596
	Jammu and Kashmir								11496
	Punjab				67767	21954	50980		140701
	Rajasthan				63815	17055	65993		146863
North-West Total					228213	88407	213058		529678
Northern	Bihar				14090				26237
	Uttar Pradesh				135942	95239	163616		394797
	Uttarakhand				19233		14754		41970
Northern Total					169265	106289	187450		463004
South-Central	Andhra Pradesh				88696	102587	194460		385743
	Telangana				61980	128457	180583		371020
South-Central Total					150676	231044	375043		756763
South-West	Karnataka				101849	49411	109434		260694
	Kerala				22020	23064	65963		111047
South-West-Total					123869	72475	175397		371741
Southern	Puducherry								13802
	Tamil Nadu				215043	85471	288717		589231
Southern Total					217873	87413	297747		603033
Western	Dadra and Nagar Haveli								
	Daman and Diu								
	Goa								
	Maharashtra				192998	95686	178472		467156
Western Total					196823	96460	179962		473245
Grand Total					1303664	803329	1745021	10327	3852014

However, it is important to note that in recent past the numbers of institutes have progressively decreased due to several factors including unwillingness of the candidates into technical education, less skilled contents in the curricula. A detailed list from last few years has provided in Table 6 (Source AICTE Handbook).

Table: 6 - Approved Institutions under AICTE from 2010-2016

AICTE Approved Institutions and Increasing Trends							
Year	Engineering	Management	MCA	Pharmacy	Architecture	HMCT	Total
2010-11							
2011-12							
2012-13							
2013-14							
2014-15							
2015-16							
2016-17							

However, in some stream the numbers of institutes are same but the numbers of seats are decreased. Although, it is worthy to mention that in few subjects, the number of institutes are remained same but with higher intake permission. In MCA (a flagship program of computing from Bachelors of diverse stream) shown less number of intake permission in 2016 than in 2015. Like MCA a number of institutions have decreased their intake number in Engineering, Management, expect pharmacy as far as 2016 data of AICTE. Table 7 depicted a detailed data into this for more clarification herewith [8], [15].

Table: 7-Variation of Intake in AICTE approved Institutions

Year	Diploma/ Post Diploma	Engineering and Technology	Management	MCA	Pharmacy	Architec ture	Hotel Management and Catering

2007-08	417923	653290	121867	70513	52334		
2008-09	610903	841018	149555	73995	64211		
2009-10	850481	1071896	179561	78293	68537		
2010-11	1083365	1314594	277811	87216	98746		
2011-12	1117545	1485894	352571	92216	102746		
2012-13	1212612	1761976	385008	100700	121652	5996	8401
2013-14	1177918	1804353	364816	119713	137257	9550	6622
2014-15	1307344	1901501	365352	109925	143244	10890	6442
2015-16	1310414	1844642	350161	103048	139622	10986	6430
2016-17	1293843	1752296	329273	94159	130926	9936	6109

Other Regulatory Bodies—

Apart from these few other regulatory bodies are also important and playing a wonderful job for the promotion and development of Education Systems as well as Information Technology systems in the nation. Among them, few important are Indian Council of Agricultural Research, National Council for Teacher Education, Rehabilitation Council of India, Medical Council of India, National Council for Rural Institutes etc. It is important to note that a majority of such institutes are located at New Delhi. A detailed on this have depicted in Table 8.

Table: 8 - Core Regulatory bodies in India in Education Sector

Sl. No.	Bodies	Abbreviations	Domain/ Field of Interest	Head Office
	All India Council for Technical Education	(AICTE)	Engineering and Management Education	New Delhi
	Distance Education Council	(DEC)	Distance & Online Education	New Delhi
	Indian Council of Agricultural Research	(ICAR)	Agriculture and Allied Sciences	New Delhi
	Bar Council of India	(BCI)	Law and Legal Studies	New Delhi
	National Council for Teacher Education	(NCTE)	Teachers Education and Physical Education	New Delhi

	Rehabilitation Council of India	(RCI)	-	New Delhi
	Medical Council of India	(MCI)	Medical Science	New Delhi
	Pharmacy Council of India	(PCI)	Pharmaceutical Sciences	New Delhi
	Indian Nursing Council	(INC)	Nursing and Allied Sciences	New Delhi
	Dental Council of India	(DCI)	Dental Sciences	New Delhi
	Central Council of Homoeopathy	(CCH)	Homoeopathy Systems	New Delhi
	Central Council of Indian Medicine	(CCIM)	Indian Medicine Systems	New Delhi
	National Council for Rural Institutes	(NCRI)	Rural Development	Telangana
	Council of Architecture	(COA)	Architecture & Design Sciences	New Delhi
	Veterinary Council of India	(VCI)	Veterinary Sciences	New Delhi
	Indian Council of Medical Research	(ICMR)	Medical & Health Sciences	New Delhi

The medical system is important and valuable for each and every nation. In India, there are many governing bodies and association in medical and health systems. Among such Indian Council of Medical Research, Medical Council of India, Dental Council of India are important. All of these have maintained their role development of medical and health research affairs. Table 9 provides the list of some of the reputed research laboratories established under the jurisdiction of Indian Council of Medical Research situated in different parts of the country [12], [22].

ICMR Research Centers at a Glance

- ✓ National Institute of Nutrition, Hyderabad (NIN), Hyderabad
 - ✓ National Centre for Laboratory Animal Science, (NCLAS) Hyderabad
 - ✓ Food and Drug Toxicology Research Centre, (FDTRC) Hyderabad
 - ✓ National Animal Resource Facility for Biomedical Research, (NARF-BR) Hyderabad
 - ✓ National Institute for Research in Tuberculosis (NIRT), Chennai
 - ✓ National Institute of Epidemiology (NIE), Chennai
 - ✓ National Institute of Malaria Research (NIMR), Delhi
 - ✓ Rajendra Memorial Research Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna
 - ✓ National Institute for Research in Reproductive Health (NIRRH), Mumbai
 - ✓ National Institute of Virology (NIV), Pune
 - ✓ Microbial Containment Complex (MCC), Pune
 - ✓ National AIDS Research Institute (NARI), Pune
 - ✓ National Institute of Occupational Health, Ahmedabad
 - ✓ National Institute of Pathology (NIP), Delhi
 - ✓ National Institute of Medical Statistics (NIMS), Delhi
 - ✓ Institute of Cytology and Preventive Oncology (ICPO), Noida
-
- ✓ Vector Control Research Centre (VCRC), Pondicherry
 - ✓ National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases (NICED), Kolkata
 - ✓ National Institute for Research in Tribal Health (NIRTH), Jabalpur
 - ✓ National Center for Disease Informatics and Research (NCDIR), Bengaluru
 - ✓ Bhopal Memorial Hospital and Research Center, (BMHRC), Bhopal
 - ✓ National Institute for Research in Environmental Health (NIREH), Bhopal
 - ✓ National JALMA institute for Leprosy & Other Mycobacterial Diseases, Agra
 - ✓ Centre for Research in Medical Entomology (CRME), Madurai
 - ✓ National Institute of Immunohaematology (NIIH), Mumbai
 - ✓ Enterovirus Research Centre (ERC), Mumbai
 - ✓ Genetic Research Centre, Mumbai
 - ✓ Desert Medicine Research Centre (DMRC), Jodhpur
 - ✓ Regional Medical Research Center, Port Blair
 - ✓ Regional Medical Research Center, Bhubaneswar
 - ✓ Regional Medical Research Centre, Dibrugarh
 - ✓ Regional Medical Research Center, Belgaum

✓ ICMR Virus Unit, Kolkata

Educational Programs in Indian Universities

Higher Education in India basically governed by the different type of institutes and academics bodies that we already learn. Now let's learn about the programs and degrees available in diverse field (only Bachelor onwards provided, ignored Diploma and lower level of study).

General Degrees

In General Stream some of the common programs and degrees include (but not limited to the following)-

- ✓ B.A. (Bachelor of Arts)
- ✓ B.Sc. (Bachelor of Science)
- ✓ B.Com. (Bachelor of Commerce)
- ✓ M.A. (Masters of Arts)
- ✓ M.Sc. (Masters of Science)
- ✓ M.Com. (Masters of Commerce)

Professional Degrees

- ✓ B.Ed. (Bachelor of Education)
- ✓ M.Ed. (Bachelor of Education)
- ✓ MCA (Master of Computer Applications)
- ✓ MBA (Master of Business Administration)

However it is important to note that apart from these few other universities are also offered programs in other different branches and that includes—

Medicine

- ✓ MBBS (Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgeon)
- ✓ MD (Doctor of Medicine)
- ✓ MS (Master of Surgeon)

Laws

- ✓ LLB. (Bachelor of Education)
- ✓ LLM
- ✓ Joint LLB (Double Degrees)-
(BA-LLB/ BSc-LLB/BCom-LLB/ BTech-LLB/BBA-LLB)
- ✓ LLD (Doctor of Laws)

Pharmacy

- ✓ B.Pharm. (Bachelor of Pharmacy)

- ✓ M.Pharm. (Master of Education)
- ✓ Pharm. D. (Doctor of Pharmacy)

Dentistry

- ✓ BDS. (Bachelor of Dental Surgery)
- ✓ MDS (Maser of Dental Surgery)

Architecture & Planning

- ✓ B.Arch. (Bachelor of Architecture)
- ✓ M.Arch. (Master of Architecture)
- ✓ M. Plan. (Master of Planning)

Designing

- ✓ B. Design (Bachelor of Design)
- ✓ M. Design. (Master of Design)

Vocational Studies

- ✓ B. Voc. (Bachelor of Vocation)
- ✓ M. Voc. (Master of Vocation)

Engineering Degrees

- ✓ B. Tech (Bachelor of Technology)
- ✓ M. Tech (Master of Technology)
- ✓ BE (Bachelor of Engineering)
- ✓ ME (Master of Engineering)
- ✓ M.Tech (Research)- Master of Technology by Research

Research Degrees

- ✓ M.Phil (Master of Philosophy)
- ✓ M.Tech (Research)- Master of Technology by Research
- ✓ Ph.D (Doctor of Philosophy)
- ✓ D.Sc (Doctor of Science)
- ✓ D.Litt (Doctor of Literature)

Professional Doctorates

- ✓ DM (Doctorate of Medicine)
- ✓ Pharm. D. (Doctor of Pharmacy)
- ✓ LLD (Doctor of Laws)
- ✓ Psy.D (Doctor of Psychology)

These are common degrees offered by the Indian universities. All the nomenclature basically listed by the UGC from time to time. It is important to note that apart from these some other degrees are also available. The MSc and BSc programs in some universities are also offered as BS and MS Program in the line of foreign universities. Some of the universities also offer MS (By Research) program. It is important to note that the general degrees are three-year duration based while masters are normally five years. Masters degrees in India needs at least five years post Higher Secondary Education (10+2), irrespective of Bachelors and Masters Duration. However, there is a misconception that a UG degree needs 3 years and PG needs 4 years. Though UG may also be more than that (such as in Laws, Medicine, Pharmacy, Engineering etc.). Lateral Entry for the qualified and eligible candidates are also increasing in recent past. The double degree programs come with at least 3+1 (i.e. 4 Years) Pattern in India.

The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) is adopted by the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) for all types of educational institutions in India. The NIRF Ranking is offered in different areas such as—

- Universities and colleges.
- Engineering institutions.
- Management institutions.
- Pharmacy institutions.
- Architecture institutions.

In this ranking system resources, research, and stakeholder perception are the key areas for this ranking. It is important to note that about 3500 institutions participated. A list of Best Engineering Institutes herewith provided in Table 10 and Table 11 depicted best 25 universities.

Table: 10- India's top ranked Engineering Institutes & Universities (Compiled from NIRF, MHRD)

Name of the Institutes	Location/Places	Rank
Indian Institute of Technology Madras	Chennai	
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay	Mumbai	
Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur	Kharagpur	
Indian Institute of Technology Delhi	New Delhi	
Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur	Kanpur	
Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee	Roorkee	
Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati	Guwahati	
Anna University	Chennai	
Jadavpur University	Kolkata	
Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad	Hyderabad	
National Institute of Technology Tiruchirappalli	Tiruchirappalli	
National Institute of Technology Rourkela	Rourkela	
Vellore Institute of Technology	Vellore	

Institute of Chemical Technology	Mumbai	
Indian Institute of Technology Indore	Indore	
Birla Institute of Technology & Science -Pilani	Pilani	
Indian Institute of Engineering Science And Technology	Howrah	
Indian Institute of Technology Bhubaneswar	Bhubaneswar	
Indian Institute of Technology Patna	Patna	
Jamia Millia Islamia	New Delhi	
Indian Institute of Technology Ropar	Rupnagar	
National Institute of Technology Surathkal	Surathkal	
Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines)	Dhanbad	
College of Engineering, Pune	Pune	
Shanmugha Arts Science Technology & Research Academy	Thanjavur	

If we notice the sharing then it is clear that among the 23 IITs only 13 are ranked into top 25 while among 3288 only 1 is received ranking. Interestingly among the 31 NITs only 3 are listed. A few Central Universities (among 47) also have Engineering Division and from that 1 Central University has ranked (Fig. 1).

Fig: 1-Sharing of Top 25 Engineering Institutes as per NIRF-2017 Ranking, Govt. of India

India holds only 1 IEST and that is also ranked into top 25. Surprisingly 4 Deemed Universities ranked into top 25, although many Institute of National Institutions and Central Institutes are not able to reach within top 25 as per the study. Among 290 State Universities 2 are listed in the Top 25 ranked Engineering institutions.

Table: 11 - India's top ranked Universities (Compiled from NIRF, MHRD)

Name of the Institutes	Location/Places	Rank
Indian Institute of Science Bangalore	Bengaluru	

Jawaharlal Nehru University	New Delhi	
Banaras Hindu University	Varanasi	
Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research	Bengaluru	
Jadavpur University	Kolkata	
Anna University	Chennai	
University of Hyderabad	Hyderabad	
University of Delhi	Delhi	
Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham	Coimbatore	
Savitribai Phule Pune University	Pune	
Aligarh Muslim University	Aligarh	
Jamia Millia Islamia	New Delhi	
Birla Institute of Technology & Science -Pilani	Pilani	
Vellore Institute of Technology	Vellore	
Indian Agricultural Research Institute	New Delhi	
Calcutta University	Kolkata	
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University	Coimbatore	
Manipal Academy of Higher Education-Manipal	Manipal	
Visva Bharti University	Bolpur	
SOA University	Bhubneswar	
Homi Bhabha National Institute	Mumbai	
Bharat University	Chennai	
Osmania University	Hyderabad	
Punjab Agriculture University	Ludhiana	
Institute of Chemical Technology	Mumbai	

Information Technology and Computing Education in India

In India most of the colleges and university departments and schools are offered programs and subjects in the bellow mentioned areas—

- *Computer Science.*
- *Computer Application.*
- *Computer Science and Engineering.*
- *Information Technology.* □ *Information Systems.*

Computer Science- Computer Science is the Science which is mathematical in nature and deals with hardcore theoretical areas such as computing logic, software systems, hardware systems, tools,

technologies and mathematics it mainly deals with Information Retrieval, Storage and dissemination. In India the common programs in this subjects are include—

- B.Sc- Computer Science
- M.Sc- Computer Science
- M.Phil- Computer Science
- Ph.D- Computer Science

Computer Application- Computer Application is another important subject dedicated for the application of computing specially software in various sectors. Computer Application is also deals with the development and management of software. Programming is the core of Computer Application domain. The nomenclatures of Computing and IT related domains (mentioned in this paper) though available worldwide but Computer Application not yet started. The common programs on Computer Applications are—

- Bachelor of Computer Application (widely available)
- Master of Computer Application (widely available & governed by AICTE)
- B.Sc- Computer Application (limited available)
- M.Sc- Computer Application (limited available)

Computer Science and Engineering- It is an important merging domain and combined with the domain of Computer Science and Computer Engineering. It is basically related with hardware engineering and mechanics and computing logics and systems development and architecture building [10]. The common program in CSE are—

- B.Tech/BE- Computer Science and Engineering
- M.Tech-ME- Computer Science and Engineering
- M.Tech (Research)- Computer Science and Engineering
- Ph.D- Computer Science and Engineering

Software Engineering-This is another domain of Computing deals with Software Engineering. Software Engineering is includes Software Development, Modeling and Knowledge Engineering, Software and Project Management and so on. The program at Bachelor of Technology level offered in few institutions. Some of the common programs are include—

- B.Tech/BE- Software Engineering
- M.Tech-ME- Software Engineering
- M.Tech (Research)- Software Engineering
- Ph.D- Software Engineering

Interestingly few institutions particularly located in South India are also offered Software Engineering program in Science stream such as –

- B.Sc- Software Engineering
- M.Sc- Software Engineering

- Ph.D- Software Engineering

Information Technology- This is an important applied science domain dedicated for the collection, selection, processing, management and dissemination of information and various technologies like Multimedia Technology, Computing, Communication Technology, Networking Technology, and Web Technology etc played an important role [11]. Some of common programs available in India are

- B.Tech/BE- Computer Science and Engineering
- M.Tech-ME- Computer Science and Engineering
- M.Tech (Research)- Computer Science and Engineering

Though it is important to note that few universities also offers program on the following nomenclatures (a very limited, most of these are interdisciplinary and applied in nature) based on their growing trends in International Universities—

- Information Science
- Information Management
- Information Systems and Management
- Informatics
- Information Science and Engineering.
- Computing and Systems Biology.
- Computational Linguistics.

Most of these subjects are available in different level of Science, Engineering and Technological Studies. Apart from these few domain based information science/IT programs and subjects are also offered such as Health Informatics/ Geo Informatics/ Library Information Science/ Bio Informatics. It is important to note that Information Science is the enhanced area of IT and Information Science also synonymously called as Informatics [5], [12].

Though apart from the universities and colleges few organizations and institutions are also offered Information Technology programs and among them National Institute of Electronics & Information Technology (NIELIT) is important. Previously it was called as DOEACC Society which was launched in 1990. Generating high quality man-power in the computer software was the initial interest of the society. Though, gradually many other areas apart from IT has been established. Rather an institution of offering classes it has become a centre for excellence of obtaining qualification (National Examination Body) in India in the field of Information Technology and Computing. Among its programs few popular are ‘O’ Level (Foundation), ‘A’ Level, ‘B’ Level ‘C’ Level (Please refer Table 12).

Table: 12-NIELIT Programs

NIELIT Programs	
Level	Equivalent to
A Level	BCA/ Bachelors in Computing/ PGDCA
B Level	MCA/ MSc-IT/Computing related areas
C Level	M.Tech/ME (IT/CSE/Computing related areas)

However the recent development of the field of Bio-Informatics has caused creation of Bio Informatics programs in different level such as BI-O/A/B level at NIELIT and offered in selected centers [5], [7], [11].

Conclusion

Education is the key element for development. Universities and educational institutions are growing rapidly in India. During 1970-1990, India received a good number of government institutions and universities. Many bodies have been developed in nation to control education systems of various fields including professional subjects and areas. In the education systems latest attribute is Distance Education Bureau (DEB). Among other subjects Information Technology is playing a great role for the development of education systems. Information Science and Computing is a diverse field and gaining rapidly around the world. Educational institutes are offering several programs in Computing & IT. The enrolment of general education as well as professional education is excelled in recent past with the introduction of different subjects and many super specialty institutions viz. IITs, NITs, IIMs and so on.

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